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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ABDULLAH bearing the USN 5SU21PT801 has completed his/her mini project on “**Critical Appraisal of two journal articles**” in the first year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AISWARYA CHANDRAN bearing the USN 5SU21PT802 has completed his/her mini project on “**Critical Appraisal of two journal articles**” in the first year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AMIYA P DESSAI bearing the USN 5SU21PT803 has completed his/her mini project on “**Critical Appraisal of two journal articles**” in the first year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ARJUN PAVITHRAN T M bearing the USN 5SU21PT804 has completed his/her mini project on “**Critical Appraisal of two journal articles**” in the first year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ARYA T K bearing the USN 5SU21PT805 has completed his/her mini project on “**Critical Appraisal of two journal articles**” in the first year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AYSHA FIDHA bearing the USN 5SU21PT806 has completed his/her mini project on **“Critical Appraisal of two journal articles”** in the first year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. CHAUDHARY JHANVI KETANBHAI bearing the USN 5SU21PT807 has completed his/her mini project on “**Critical Appraisal of two journal articles**” in the first year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. JISHNU MOHAN M P bearing the USN 5SU21PT808 has completed his/her mini project on “**Critical Appraisal of two journal articles**” in the first year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. JOONA A bearing the USN 5SU21PT809 has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. KADAM VIDYA NARAYANRAO bearing the USN 5SU21PT810 has completed his/her mini project on “**Critical Appraisal of two journal articles**” in the first year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. KEERTHANA R bearing the USN 5SU21PT811 has completed his/her mini project on **“Critical Appraisal of two journal articles”** in the first year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. PAI PURVA PURUSHOTTAM bearing the USN 5SU21PT812 has completed his/her mini project on “**Critical Appraisal of two journal articles**” in the first year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. PATIL SHIVANI ASHOK bearing the USN 5SU21PT813 has completed his/her mini project on “**Critical Appraisal of two journal articles**” in the first year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. RAGENDHU S bearing the USN 5SU21PT814 has completed his/her mini project on **“Critical Appraisal of two journal articles”** in the first year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. NAGAR RICHI RAMESHKUMAR bearing the USN 5SU21PT815 has completed his/her mini project on “**Critical Appraisal of two journal articles**” in the first year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SARA SHIVA KUMAR bearing the USN 5SU21PT816 has completed his/her mini project on “**Critical Appraisal of two journal articles**” in the first year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SHAIKH UZMA SHAKILAHMED bearing the USN 5SU21PT817 has completed his/her mini project on “**Critical Appraisal of two journal articles**” in the first year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SIDDESH G bearing the USN 5SU21PT818 has completed his/her mini project on “**Critical Appraisal of two journal articles**” in the first year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SOLANKI RISHIKESH DEVENDRABHAI bearing the USN 5SU21PT819 has completed his/her mini project on “**Critical Appraisal of two journal articles**” in the first year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SWETA PATNAIK bearing the USN 5SU21PT820 has completed his/her mini project on “**Critical Appraisal of two journal articles**” in the first year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. T SUJAY KUMAR REDDY bearing the USN 5SU21PT821 has completed his/her mini project on “**Critical Appraisal of two journal articles**” in the first year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. TENZIN GYALZIN bearing the USN 5SU21PT822 has completed his/her mini project on “**Critical Appraisal of two journal articles**” in the first year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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